

TECH TOOLS FOR BOTH ONLINE AND OFFLINE CLASSROOMS FOR FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT AND TEACHER DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: Technology has already been indivisible part of people's lives. It has already found its way into teaching too. Today, teaching is far more interesting than before thanks to this advancement. This article discusses the role and need of technology in classrooms and looks through a number of tools to use in classrooms for two main purposes: formative assessment in class and teacher development for lesson preparation

Key words: Formative assessment, teacher development, offline classes, online classes, kahoot, bamboozle, quizziz, padlet, canva, screencastify.

1 INTRODUCTION

"In today's schools and classrooms learning with technology is of utmost importance" says Kouser and Majid [1] who discusses the role of technology in classrooms. Global educational systems, researchers, parents, governments, leaders, and instructors see technology as a critical component of a child's education. It was acknowledged in Australia that technology changes impact people's ways of sharing, generating, utilizing, and developing knowledge in society. Besides, current and upcoming trends require being skilled in ICT (information and communication technologies). The major motivations for adopting technology in education are to prepare students for society and to stay up with society.

Researchers and educators have turned to technology as a means of enhancing learners' motivation and engagement. Adapting to different learning styles and enhancing learning outcomes. The instructor employs different technology tools for the learners to make the teaching-learning process more effective, and the technological tools assist enhance the effective teaching-learning process. Instructors can utilize new technology in the teaching-learning process to develop their assessments and communicate the assignments to the students for whom it is designed [2].

2 TEACHER DEVELOPMENT

There are a lot of benefits of using tech tools in classroom. Although one might believe that technology is only a diversion, it can really support active learning in the classroom. Traditionally, dry subjects may be made dynamic and enjoyable by using technology in your classroom, such as a computer, tablet, or other electronic device. As every student in a class is unique, it might be difficult to modify the lesson plan to suit each one of them. Thankfully, educational technology may assist you in changing your classes. While employing technology in the classroom, teachers have

noticed an increase in the number of instances where students assist one another. Many technology-based tasks need the use of additional resources, which puts pupils in a position where they must ask their classmates or the instructor for assistance. Furthermore, when students are divided into small groups, the more technologically savvy pupils may help their less skilled counterparts.

According to the Council of Chief State School Officers (CCSSO), formative assessment is used during instruction to elicit evidence of learning to improve student understanding. Implementing digital tools in the classroom for formative assessment can be beneficial for both teachers and students. Dynamic formative assessment allows teachers to use real-time data to guide their instruction and get students back on track.

3 FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT

Formative assessment processes are effective if they have the following four characteristics: clear learning goals: Students should understand what they're working on [3]. They must be able to explain what targeted understanding, performance, or skill they're working toward, how they'll know when they've reached that target, and how to gauge their progress along the way.

Needless to say, *kahoot* is one of the most used platforms at nearly all educational institutions including schools, academic lyceums, and Universities. The platform is a global learning platform company that wants to empower everyone, including children, students, and employees, to unlock their full learning potential. This learning platform makes it easy for any individual or corporation to create, share, and host learning sessions that drive compelling engagement. Kahoot sessions can be hosted anywhere, in person or virtually, using any device with an internet connection.

Quizizz is a Learning platform that offers multiple tools to make a classroom fun, interactive and engaging. As a teacher, you can create lessons, conduct formative

assessments, assign homework, and have other interactions with your students (for all grades) in a captivating way. Quizizz features: Instructor paced Lessons/Quizzes: Teachers control the pace; the whole class goes through each question together.

Bamboozle is an online-based learning platform that uses games to teach. It offers a wide selection of games to get your students started right away but you can also add your own. As a result, the library of content is growing daily as teachers add their own challenges to the resource pool. Bamboozle is a good option both for in class use and remote learning as well as homework. Since students can access it from their own devices, it's possible to game and learn from almost anywhere.

Wordwall can be used to create both interactive and printable activities. Most of our templates are available in both an interactive and a printable version.

Interactives are played on any web-enabled device, like a computer, tablet, phone or interactive whiteboard. They can be played individually by students, or be teacher-led with students taking turns at the front of the class.

Teacher Development publishes articles on all aspects of teachers' professional development [4-5]. It acts as a forum for critical and reflective attention to practice in teacher development and aims thereby to contribute to the quality of professional development. The journal takes a 'whole-career' view of teacher development, and work from both international and inter-professional perspectives is welcome.

Canva is an Australian graphic design platform that is used to create social media graphics and presentations. The app includes readymade templates for users to use, and the platform is free and offers paid subscriptions such as Canva Pro and Canva for Enterprise for additional functionality. In 2021, Canva launched a video editing tool. Users can also pay for physical products to be printed and shipped. The company has announced it intends to compete with Google and Microsoft in the office software category, with website and whiteboard products. Padlet takes the idea of the notice board and makes it digital, so it's enhanced. This creates a space for teachers and students in education to share but in a way that's actually better than the real-world version. Unlike a physical notice board, this space can be populated with rich media, including words and images as well as videos and links too. All that and it's instantly updated for anyone sharing the space to see right away.

Work in a single document with teammates or people outside your company. See edits as others type, communicate through built-in chat and ask questions through including comments. Track changes made to

your documents and undo anything you choose. Previous versions are kept indefinitely and they don't count toward your storage.

Screenastify is a powerful app that allow teachers to capture important moments online that can help save time and enhance learning in the long run. Since Screenastify is an extension it's easy to install, use, and run across most devices. Screenastify lets you record video from your device to playback later and share. You can even edit the video to perfect it before you put it to good use. That means being able to give a presentation across multiple websites, with highlights on the screen and your face in the corner via webcam, to name just one option.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the speed of technology adoption in society and in schools has been exponential and will remain so. Technology is helping teachers in their duty of giving pupils guidance and structure, monitoring progress, and evaluating their performance. Students use technology to carry out research projects, analyze data, solve issues, build products, and evaluate their own work. For the purpose of generating and expressing new information and understandings, students might collaborate with others. The techniques based on learning theories that enable teachers to provide their pupils various learning opportunities.

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